

Analysis of Neoplastic Lesions of Thyroid with TIRADS and BETHESDA Correlation in a Tertiary Care Centre

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Abstract:

Introduction: Neoplastic lesions of the thyroid include benign and malignant tumors which require thyroidectomy to categorise the lesions, its extent and to determine further therapeutic management.

Aim: 1. To identify the most prevalent neoplastic lesions, sex and age wise distribution. 2. To analyse the correlation of the available TIRADS, BETHESDA categories with the histopathology diagnosis of the neoplasm.

Settings and Design: This study was conducted in the Institute of Pathology, Madras Medical College, and Tamil Nadu from January 2022 to December 2023. It is a retrospective study in which all the thyroidectomy specimens received were subjected to histopathological examination and the details of the available TIRADS and BETHESDA categories were obtained.

Materials and Methods: After the Histopathology examination, the neoplastic lesions including benign and malignant were analysed as per age and sex using Microsoft office (excel and word). Neoplastic lesions with Bethesda and TIRADS category correlation is assessed using SPSS software.

Results and Conclusions: Of the 234 neoplastic lesions, 78.2% seen in females and 21.7% were seen in males. Papillary carcinoma thyroid occupied 64.5% and rare neoplasms like Langerhans cell histiocytosis, Non-Hodgkin lymphoma, Anaplastic and Medullary carcinoma occupies 0.8%, 1.28%, 2.13%, 1.28% respectively. TIRADS (88 cases) and BETHESDA (131 cases) were analysed. Correlation of more than 95 percentage seen in tirads 4 and 5, Bethesda 5 and 6 with the histopathology diagnosis. Meticulous examination and analysing the lesions using the essential and desirable criteria as per WHO can aid in the accurate diagnosis.

Keywords: Tumors Of Thyroid, Radiological And Cytopathological Correlation, Statistical Analysis.

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Introduction

Thyroid disorders come to clinical attention due to enlargement of thyroid gland (goitre), or hormonal level variations and its related clinical symptoms.

Thyroid gland is an endocrine organ in which the functional unit is the thyroid follicle. The follicle is lined by follicular epithelial cells and the lumen encloses colloid. Parafollicular cells are seen adjacent to the follicles.

Follicular cell derived neoplasms are classified as benign, low risk neoplasms, and malignant neoplasm whereas parafollicular cell derived neoplasm is medullary carcinoma. Other non-epithelial cell neoplasms though rare still exists. In this study all the neoplastic conditions of thyroid

are analysed, the frequency of those neoplasms, age and sex wise distribution of the lesions are studied for a period of two years.

Materials and Methods

It is a retrospective study carried out in the Institute of Pathology from the period of January 2022 to December 2023, 2 years.

All the surgical thyroidectomy specimens were analysed using haematoxylin and eosin sections, when needed immunohistochemistry evaluation done for the cases with diagnostic difficulties.

All the neoplastic lesions are classified based on the histomorphological features (at times

immunohistochemistry) as benign or malignant and the malignant lesions are sub-classified as per WHO guidelines 2022.

Inclusion criteria: All the neoplastic lesions of thyroid.

Exclusion criteria: Non-neoplastic lesions of thyroid and neoplasm of parathyroid.

Statistical analysis: The data are tabulated using Microsoft office

Results

We received 748 thyroidectomy specimens which include lobectomy, hemithyroidectomy, total thyroidectomy, and completion thyroidectomy for various clinical reasons. Out of 748 specimens neoplastic cases including benign and malignant were 234 (31%)

Out of those 234 cases 183 (78%) were females, and 51 (21%) were males. Male female ratio being 1:4. Total number of benign neoplasms were 42 and the low risk and malignant neoplasm were 192 cases, constituting 18 % and 72% respectively.

In females, the commonest age group affected for benign and malignant cases is 21 to 40 yrs.

In males, the commonest age group affected is more than 60 years for benign and 41 to 60 years for malignancy.

Among the benign neoplastic category, follicular adenoma constitutes 33 cases (14 %), oncocytic adenoma were 9 cases (3.8%). Both the benign entities show female preponderance. One case of follicular adenoma in a 47 year old female is associated with parathyroid adenoma. Youngest

age and sex of follicular adenoma in our study is 16 years female. In our study ,of the low risk neoplasm, NIFTP* Non-invasive follicular thyroid neoplasm with papillary like nuclear features were 20 cases (11%) which was seen in females only, Well Differentiated tumour of Uncertain malignant potential* WDTUMP was 1 case (0.4%).

Of the malignant neoplasm, papillary carcinoma constitutes 151 cases (75%), follicular carcinoma 3 cases(1.2%), Oncocytic carcinoma- 2 cases (2%), Poorly differentiated thyroid carcinoma - 4 cases (1%), Medullary Carcinoma thyroid -3 cases(2%), Anaplastic carcinoma -7 cases (5%), Non-hodgkin lymphoma-3 cases (1%), Langerhans cell histiocytosis -2 cases (2%).

Among the papillary thyroid carcinoma we have reported the following variants as follows:

i) papillary micro carcinoma- 12 cases, ii)classic type - 105 cases,(iii) follicular variant of papillary ca- 13 cases iv)mixed patterns tall cell, columnar and solid pattern - 1 case v).hobnail 1 case vi) hobnail and warthin variant -1 case (seen in same tumour), vi). Oncocytic variant- 1 case.

We have noticed multifocality in 18 cases as 12 cases in micro carcinoma and 4 cases in papillary carcinoma classic type and 2 cases in follicular variants of pap CA. Among the 12 cases of papillary micro carcinoma, 9 cases show hashimoto thyroiditis in the background. One case shows papillary carcinoma classic type associated with caseating granulomatous lymphadenitis in the central neck node dissection specimen.

One case of anaplastic carcinoma was associated with papillary carcinoma classic type.

Table 1: Neoplastic Cases with Male, Female Distribution

S. No	Histologic Type	Male	Female	Total
Benign Neoplasm		Number Of Cases With Percentage		
1	Follicular adenoma	6 (2.5%)	27(11.5%)	33 (14%)
2	Oncocytic adenoma	2 (0.8%)	7 (2.9%)	9 (3.8%)
Low Risk Neoplasm				
3	Non-invasive follicular thyroid neoplasm with papillary-like nuclear features (NIFTP)	-	20 (8.5%)	20 (8.5%)
4	Well differentiated tumour of uncertain malignant potential (WDTUMP)	1 (0.4%)	1 (0.4%)	2 (0.8%)
Malignant Neoplasm				
5	Follicular thyroid carcinoma	-	3 (1.28%)	3 (1.28%)
7	Papillary thyroid carcinoma(PTC)	34 (14.5%)	117 (50%)	151 (64.5%)
8	Oncocytic carcinoma thyroid	1 (0.4%)	1 (0.4%)	2 (0.8%)
9	Poorly differentiated thyroid carcinoma(PDTC)	1 (0.4%)	3 (1.28%)	4 (1.7%)
10	Medullary Carcinoma thyroid	1 (0.4%)	2 (0.8%)	3 (1.28%)
11	Anaplastic carcinoma	3 (1.28%)	2 (0.8%)	5 (2.13%)
12	Non hodgkin lymphoma(NHL)	2 (0.8%)	1 (0.4%)	3 (1.28%)
13	Langerhans cell histiocytosis (LCH)	-	2 (0.8%)	2 (0.8%)
	Total	51 (21.7%)	186 (78.2%)	237 (100%)

Table 2: Age Distribution Of Neoplastic Lesions Of Thyroid `

Neoplasm	11-20 yrs		21-40 yrs		41-60 yrs		>60 yrs		Total		Total
	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	
Follicular adenoma	5	-	13	2	8	2	1	2	27	6	33
Oncocytic adenoma	-	-	2	-	3	2	2	-	7	2	9
NIFTP	1	-	11	-	5	-	3	-	20	-	20
WDTUMP	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	1	1	2
follicular carcinoma	-	-	-	-	-	1	2	-	2	1	3
Papillary thyroid carcinoma	3	-	47	14	53	12	15	7	119	34	151
Oncocytic carcinoma	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	1	1	2
PDTC	-	-	1	-	1	1	1	-	3	1	4
Medullary Carcinoma	-	-	-	1	1	-	1	-	2	1	3
Anaplastic carcinoma	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	2	3	2	5
NHL	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2	1	2	3
LCH	-	-	1	-	-	-	1	-	2	-	2
TOTAL	9	-	73	17	63	22	29	13	184	51	235

On analysing the TI-RADS, and BETHESDA categorisation with the neoplastic lesions confirmed histopathologically our results were tabulated in table 3 and 4. TIRADS 1,2,3 were grouped as one category as that indicates normal, benign and probably benign respectively. Whereas tirads 3,4 were grouped together since that denotes suspicious of malignancy and malignancy. Upon analysing 17 cases of malignancy reported within the TIRADS benign group, 12 cases were found to be papillary microcarcinoma which couldn't be traced radiologically. BETHESDA categories were

grouped into three as Bethesda 2(benign), Bethesda 3 and 4 as indeterminate group [since that could turn as benign or malignant neoplasm], Bethesda 5 and 6 as malignant group. 18 malignant cases were categorised as Bethesda 2, in which 12 cases were microcarcinoma. Hence the risk of malignancy is shown as 69%. We would like to emphasise that in our institute we analyse the entire sections of both lobes hence the chance of diagnosing microcarcinoma (only microscopically) is higher.

Table 3: Histopathological and Tirads Correlation:

Neoplasm	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	Total
Follicular adenoma	2	15	12	1	-	30
Oncocytic adenoma	-	4	3	-	-	7
NIFTP	-	-	-	1	1	22
Papillary thyroid carcinoma	-	8	7	22	5	62
Oncocytic carcinoma	-	-	1	-	-	1
Follicular carcinoma	-	-	1	-	-	1
Medullary Carcinoma	-	-	-	1	-	1
Poorly differentiated carcinoma	-	-	-	1	-	1
Anaplastic carcinoma	-	-	-	1	2	3
Non hodgkin lymphoma	-	-	-	2	-	2
Langerhans cell histiocytosis	-	-	-	1	-	1
Total Benign Neoplasm (N=32)	2	11	15	1	0	
Total Malignant Neoplasm (N=52)	0	8	9	28	7	
Total	2	27	21			88

Table 4: Statistical Analysis of Tirads and Neoplastic Lesions:

Tirads	Benign	Malignant	total	Chi sq	P Value	ROM*	OR*	95% OR
Tirads 1,2 And 3	27	17	44	28.72	<0.01	38.64	58.76	7.36-468.9
Tirads 4,5	1	37	38			97.37		
Total	28	54	82			65.85		
Sensitivity	96.43%							
Specificity	68.52%							
PPV	61.36%							
NPV	97.37%							

Rom: Risk of Malignancy, OR: Odds Ratio, PPV: Positive Predictive Value, NPV: Negative Predictive Value

Table 5: Histopathological and Bethesda Correlation:

Neoplasm	Bethesda 1	Bethesda 2	Bethesda 3	Bethesda 4	Bethesda 5	Bethesda 6	Total
Follicular adenoma	1	6	9	13	-	-	29
Oncocytic adenoma	-	2		2		-	4
NIFTP		5	2	1			
Papillary thyroid carcinoma	2	18	9	4	15	21	79
Oncocytic carcinoma	-	-	1	1	-		2
Follicular carcinoma	-	-	1	-	-		1
Medullary Carcinoma	-	-	-	-			
PDTC	-	-	-	-	1		1
Anaplastic carcinoma	-	-			2	4	6
NHL	-	-	-			2	2
LCH	-	-	-		1	1	2
total benign(N=36)	2	19	2	12		0	
total malignant(N=95)	2	23	11	5	21	28	
Total	4	47	13	17	22	28	131

Table: 6 Statistical Analysis of Bethesda and Neoplastic Lesions

Bethesda	Benign	Malignant	Total	Chi Square	P Value	ROM*
Bethesda II	8	18	26	14.54	0.0001	69.23
Bethesda III, IV	24	16	40			40.00
Bethesda V,VI	0	49	49			100.00
Total	32	83	115			72.17

Discussion

Thyroid disorders presents as enlargement of thyroid gland, or as varied clinical presentations due to increase or decrease of thyroid hormone levels. Thyroidectomies are being done for various reasons like enlargement of thyroid gland causing compressive symptoms, suspicious thyroid nodules and in few cases of hyper and hypothyroidism. Histopathological examination remains mainstay in determining the treatment by identifying the non-neoplastic and neoplastic lesions, categorizing the neoplasm, its extent, grade and staging.

Thyroid neoplasm incidence has been steadily increasing over the decades. In India, an estimation of 38,5749 (including males and females) cases would be diagnosed per year in 2025 [15]. As per National Cancer Registry Programme of ICMR (Indian Council OF Medical Research), Kerala state in India reported the highest incidence of thyroid Cancer. [15]

Among the neoplastic lesions commonest one being papillary thyroid carcinoma (65%). similar to Biren et al and Dilasma et al [1,2] Male female ratio being 1:4 similar to study by Mahesh et al [3]. In our study, the frequencies of lesions commonly seen in the age group, in females is 21 to 40 years, in males 41 to 60 years. This study shows benign neoplasm as 25% and the malignant neoplasm as 75%, similar to other studies.[3,4] The incidence of follicular adenoma in our study is (14%) which is similar to the study by Dilasma et al (13.5%). Other studies also reported that follicular adenoma was the commonest benign neoplasm[1] with the

incidence as 7.5%[1] but they have analysed for a period of 1 year.

Non-invasive follicular thyroid neoplasm with papillary like nuclear features is the low risk neoplasm included in recent WHO classification. Though the exact incidence of this type not being reported in literature, one study by Mohammed al Hasan et al [12], analysed 15 consecutive cases of NIFTP .He reported as 73 % of female preponderance with the mean age group affected as 40 years which is similar to our study where we reported all the cases in female patients.

Papillary carcinoma is the commonest neoplasm being reported in literature. Study by paras Gayatri devi et al is similar to our study, in which they studied papillary neoplasm for a period of 3 years. They reported 44 cases of Pap CA whereas our study shows 151 cases. Classic type is the commonest variant similar to Devi et al [4].

Oncocytic carcinoma thyroid is being reported with incidence of 3 to 5 %. [6] It is a follicular cell derived neoplasm comprising >75% of oncocytic cells with lack of nuclear features of papillary carcinoma, and shows vascular and capsular invasion. we report 2 cases of oncocytic carcinoma one in a 53 years male and another one in 54 year female, commonest age group affected as per amenable Syed et al [6].out of two cases, one case a 54 female presented with neck mass, whereas 53 male presented with neck mass and skeletal metastasis similar tovia j r et al [5] Medullary carcinoma is a neoplasm of parafollicular c cells, and were diagnosed based on its histomorphology pattern and nuclear features. It is a rare malignancy

accounting for 1 to 10 percentage of all thyroid neoplasm. Recent literature review shows variants of medullary thyroid carcinoma like double Negative form [7], mixed Medullary with follicular carcinoma, papillary and medullary carcinomas [8]. Our cases display characteristic histomorphology and immunohistochemistry of medullary thyroid carcinoma.

Anaplastic thyroid carcinoma is a highly aggressive neoplasm with rapid clinical course and has a high rate of mortality and morbidity with the incidence being 2 to 3 percent of thyroid neoplasms. The mean age affected in our study is more than 60 years, similar to jing yang et al., [9]. With no much difference in the incidence among gender. We reported 5 cases of anaplastic carcinoma in our institute for a period of two years. In which three cases show sarcomatoid morphology and two cases show squamous and sarcomatoid morphology. In the core needle biopsy, the squamous component made us think of the possibility of extension of squamous cell carcinoma from the aerodigestive tract.

Non Hodgkin lymphoma as primary thyroid neoplasm is very rare accounting for less than 5 percent [10]. We encountered three cases of DLBCL (Diffuse large cell lymphoma) all were more than 60 years old, male and females and showed a background of hashimoto thyroiditis, similar to Saidha et al. [10]. Identifying lymphoma in FNAC is very important as many times lymphocytic thyroiditis, and hashimoto thyroiditis may pose diagnostic difficulty. In such cases history and radiological correlation should be kept in mind to avoid the underdiagnosis in Fine needle aspiration specimens.

Langerhans cell histiocytosis though rare, we encountered 2 cases in thyroid, both in females. Age affected is 38 and 60 years female, as a part of multisystem disease similar to Yadav et al. [11] So far 75 cases of LCH thyroid been reviewed in literature which shows male to female ratio as 1: 1.4. [11] It pose a diagnostic difficulty in fine needle aspiration cytology as the histiocytoid morphology may mislead to granulomatous thyroiditis, and the nuclear grooves may confuse with papillary carcinoma thyroid. These rare lesions should always be kept in mind to make accurate diagnosis.

On reviewing literature for TIRADS and BETHESDA correlation study by Joanan grace et al [15]. Yashwant singh ratore et al [14] shows the risk of malignancy in TIRADS 5, BETHESDA 5 and 6 as 100%, Similar to our study.

Conclusion:

Thyroid neoplasms show diverse histomorphological features but the commonest

neoplasm in the benign were follicular adenoma and the malignant neoplasm were papillary thyroid carcinoma. All the neoplastic lesions show female preponderance. There was a good concordance among the TIRADS 4,5, Bethesda 5,6 with the histopathology diagnosis.

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